

JUBAIL UNIVERSITY COLLEGE ADVISORY PROGRAM

STUDENTS' SATISFACTION LEVEL AS PERCEIVED BY MALE AND FEMALE BRANCHES

A COMPARATIVE STUDY at JUBAIL UNIVERSITY COLLEGE (JUC): KINGDOM OF SAUDI ARABIA

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to find out information regarding the advisory program at Jubail University College both male and female branches. For this research compare the results to make recommendations for improving the current advisory program. The tool that has been used to collect information include open-ended survey questionnaire prepared on Google forms. The participants of this study is 350 students in this survey that include both male and female branches that contain different specializations and levels of the study in the university. Based on the findings of this research, it has been found that female students are more satisfied with the current advisory program and attend advisory sessions on a regular basis, while the majority of male students do not attend advisory sessions.

Keywords: Jubail University College (JUC), Satisfaction level, Male and female Students, Advisory program.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper evaluates the students' satisfaction level of Academic Advisory committee of Jubail University. It has been identified that Academic Advisory Committee (AAC) was formed by Managing Directors (MD), which includes coordinators of different departments. In this

committee coordinator representing students including MALE and FEMALES for the student advisory program. This program was developed for multi purposes in the university that includes; helping the students in selecting programs, provide an understanding of academic policies and procedures of Jubail University College (JUC). Furthermore, this committee evaluates and monitor the academic performance and attendance of students in different courses to assist them for achieving their academic goals. In addition, this program enhances students' awareness about educational resources and services provided by JUC. (e.g., field training, tutoring, and other support services to students that assist students to select courses that are appropriate for them and that would highlight their strengths in a specific field. Moreover, this committee provided support to promote positive working relationships amongst the students, their advisors, faculty members, and other staff members of JUC.

The process of the advisory program is based on different stages which include as follow; it starts with the (MD) who forms the advisory committee every academic year for two branches of male and female. In the second step, the committee is formed which include a chairperson, a deputy chairperson and one coordinator for each department. After that, every faculty in each department is considered as an advisor, and every advisor in each department is assigned some students in his major for advisory. The next step of advisory committee contains the prep year students those are advised by the General

Studies and English departments. On the contrary, the major students are advised by faculty members from their department. After that, every advisor reports back to his department coordinator. Finally, every coordinator reports back to the committee chairperson or the deputy chairperson of the committee.

The university is considered one of the most important stages in which the individuals has gone throughout in his life. Within the campus, the individual acquires new skills and enters into personal and collective relationships. These relationships vary in motives and methods. Students learn how to choose and acquire the mental values, so it is a transitional stage; moving from its small environment to a more interactive and attractive environment. This element makes students to face directly with difficult conditions and situations of life and various conflicts. In addition to the developmental, psychological and social changes and needs to be achieved in a specific period (Holian, 2006: 1129, Santa, 2016).

However, this research paper will explore the role of information technology in business innovation. Simultaneously, the significance of IT in business innovation will be highly focused to move the organizations towards success [2,4]. Further, the role of technical architecture and social architecture of the organizations will be highlighted for IT-enabled business innovation.

Problem Statement

This study is aimed to determine the students' satisfaction level about Jubail University College (JUC) advisory program. It seeks to answer the following:

1. What is the best way of meeting with your advisor?
2. What is the students' satisfaction level of (JUC) advisory program?
3. What is the percentage of students attending advisory sessions?

Scope and Delimitations

This study was conducted to evaluate the students' satisfaction level about (JUC) advisory program. Based on the findings, the recommendation will be provided to the Academic Advisory Committee to improve the current program.

One of the biggest limitations that the researcher has faced is the number of participants which was 350

out of 3000 students (containing both male and female branches).

2. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study will serve as the basis to guide JUC, and other institution and the result will benefit the following: Jubail University College: for improving the current advisory program.

Other universities and colleges: they can use the finding to serve as a model for adopting new ways to improve the current advisory program they have.

The researcher: it will give the opportunity to acquire new knowledge.

Other researchers: they can use this study as a reference and make the further evaluation advisory program.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

From the study of McCulloch, et al. (2016) it has been found that development of relationships with students is the vital element for advisory committee in universities. In relation to this, it has been recognized that student relationships connect students with different members of the university including teachers, other students. Moreover, advisory committee also connects teachers with other teachers. This increase collaboration that leads effective educational system. In contrast to this, development of advisory committee has supported for creating control over activities, developed structure group caring and friendly environment where the interaction of teacher with students are made on different levels [2].

According to Benson, (2013) who specified that in an advisory program students meet regularly with an advisor throughout the complete educational program. The purpose of the advisory program is to provide better assistance to every student and to mentor them for several activities. In addition to this, Ayres (2014) pointed out that advisory program does not contain any academic lecture or classes as it is the combination of several activities and discussion group for counseling students regarding their selected field. Moreover, the interaction of advisor with advises tending to be supportive and less pressure in universities. Furthermore, Turner, Straub, and Kathryn Wagner (2017) indicated that advisory committees are developed in universities for developing a community that promotes observational learning, educational success, to develop a plan for

postsecondary and providing support for the communities where certain tragedies occur.

In relation to this, McGill (2017) indicated that application of advisory program in university extends the traditional role of the teacher from the primary focus of delivering content to development of students. In addition to this, the effective advisory services include activities, group discussion, and routine activities within the university. Stacey (2016) pointed out that activities of advisory committees aim to developed youth and community. However, most of the new advisors in educational feel awkward for development of such activities in an educational institute. As the review of some new advisors elaborated that they are assigned to the completely new task for work permanently and managing effective business flow [4]. In contrast to this, Dean et al., (2018) identify that new advisor makes an alteration in plans and add more activities that take place during class within the comfort zone of students and advisors. In this regard, Field et al., (2014) suggested that teacher can develop different activities within the class by changing class structure and development of group and encourage face to face discussion. The comfort zone of teachers are developed for the short-term, but they avoid to take long-term risk of learning to be an advisor.

4. METHODOLOGY

The method of this research is primary quantitative which identify the level of satisfaction among students of Jubail University College regarding the advisory program. To determine the required number of the sample from the whole population of student, following formula was used to identify a sample of the research.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N e^2}$$

n = the required number of sample.

N = the population of Jubail University College (3000 Student).

e = Margin of error (5%).

Sources of Data

This research is based on primary source of data. The primary source of data in this research is a survey which was obtained online by using Google forms. The respondents of the study were 350 students from different departments and levels that contain students from the male and female campus of the university.

Assumptions

1. The students are not satisfied with the current program.
2. 40% of the students do not attend the advisory session.
3. The best way of meeting with advisors is online meetings.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The survey yields a total of 350 responses from students both males and females from different specialization and levels. For the quantitative analysis of collected data Excel sheet was used with application of some statistical functions to analyze the data. The comparison of data is based on analysis of many aspects including, field, level, number of visits per semester and the way students prefer to meet their advisors with.

Respondents in Terms of Gender

Figure 1: Gender proportion

Respondents in Terms of Gender

Figure 2: Number of Participants

From the calculation of participants, it has been identified that proportion of male students in the research is higher than the proportion of female students. The above figure shows the percentage and number of the students by classifying them in gender. From this, it has been identified that the majority of participants were male, representing 57% of the sample (200 students) and female participants were 43% of the sample (150 students).

Figure 3: Classification of students

The above figure shows the number of students who participated in the study in terms of their major subjects. It can be clearly seen that the majority of male students were from Civil Engineering representing (CE) 57 students, Mechanical Engineering (ME) with a 49 student, Management Information System (MIS) ranked as third with 46 student, lastly Business Administration (BUS) and Computer Science (CS) got students were 31 and 17 students respectively.

On the other hand, female participant of the research in which the majority were from (MIS) with 41 students, 35 students from Interior Design (ID). In addition English (ENG), (CS) and (BUS) students were 32, 22, 20 students respectively. Moreover, there are some subjects that are offered to only female or male. Therefore results show 0 participants in that field

Terms of Level

Figure 4: Student level

The above figure represents the different levels of participants based on their year of education. From the evaluation of above figure, it has been found that the majority of the participant were males that were from Freshmen with 55 students, followed by Sophomore with 53 students, then Junior, Senior and Preparatory participant include 46, 45, 1 respectively. In contrast to this, research participant from the female branch includes the majority of Junior level students with 49 students that is followed by Senior level students with 34 students, Sophomore, Freshmen, and Preparatory with 33, 28, and six respectively.

Figure 5: Satisfaction level

The main focus of this research on evaluation of students' satisfaction level. In relation to this above figure shows the number of students and their satisfaction level toward the advisory process. It has been found from collected data that females are more satisfied with the advising process in university. In addition, from the collected data researcher identify that male students' satisfaction level is low compared to female students' satisfaction level.

Figure 6: Knowing Advisors

Figure 7: knowing Advisors

Based on the above results, it has been identified that the majority of both males and females know their advisors, but for males, there is a 9.50% of the sample who do not know their advisors. This is quite a high percentage as compared to females in which only 0.85%.

Figure 8: Number of students Visits

The above figure presents the quantitative data of students include a number of visits per semester. In this regard, it is clearly seen that the majority of male students do not attend advising sessions in university. Furthermore, the finding of the research reveals that the majority of female students visit their advisors more than twice per semester. This implied that the female branch is adopting effective strategies that motivate female students to meet their advisors as compared to male students.

Figure 9: Student Preferences

The above figure represents students' preferences for different forms of meeting with advisors. From this, it has been found that the majority of male and

female students prefers face-to-face meetings, which may be considered better because it allows a student to express his feelings better than online meetings or texting with an advisor.

6. SUMMARY

After analyzing the collected data, it has been found that the majority of students prefer face-to-face meetings. Moreover, the satisfaction level of majority male students is low as compared to the satisfaction of female students who are satisfied with the current procedures and processes of the advisory program. In addition to this, the percentage of male students who attend advising sessions is very low as compared to female students. In relation to this, Mr. Mamoun Deputy Chairperson of AAC assured to researchers that this is what researcher noticed from the survey where researcher asked the respondents from an open-ended question "if you have any suggestions to improve the current advisory program, please feel free to write your suggestions (optional)". The majority of male responses were negative, like "Sometimes when I met my advisor I feel like he is busy so I do not like this feeling when I meet him.", "Sometimes the advisor does not have the information I need.", "just waste of time". While female responses were positive, like "our advisors' helped me a lot", "Every student should have one period in his schedule as advisory class

7. RECOMMENDATION

Since the percentage of female branch students' who attend advising sessions are more satisfied with current advising process is higher than the male branch students. It is recommended that the male branch require to adopt the strategies that female branch is following to increase the number of male students attending sessions to increase the satisfaction level of male students. Also, the management needs to conduct the meeting with the students to make them aware about the advisory program and its importance for the students.

8. REFERENCES

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9. APPENDIX

Appendix A: Screen shots of the data interpretation using Microsoft Excel

Gender	Respondents
Male.	200
Female.	150

Vists	Male	Female
More than twice per semester	3	51
twice a semester	14	45
Once a semester	53	28
None	130	26

Satisfaction Level	Male	Female
Strongly Satisfied	1	55
Satisfied	17	51
Neutral	66	32
Not Satisfied	73	10
Strongly Not Satisfied	43	2

Ways	Male	Female
face-to-face	99	108
Online meetings	45	28
Online chat (e.g. whatsapp)	56	14

Appendix B: Screenshots of the Questionnaire

What is your name ? (optional)

Your answer

What is your gender? *

- Male.
- Female.

What is your major? *

- Business Administration (BUS)
- Management Information System (MIS)
- Mechanical Engineering (ME)
- Civil Engineering (CE)
- Computer Science (CS)
- Interior Design (ID)
- English (ENG)

What level you are in? *

- Preparatory
- Freshmen
- Sophomore
- Junior
- Senior

Do you know your adviser? *

- Yes.
- No.

How often do you visit your adviser? *

- More than twice per semester
- twice a semester
- Once a semester
- None

Which way you prefer to meet with your adviser? *

- face-to-face
- Online meetings
- Online chat (e.g. whatsapp)

Are you satisfied with the current advising process? *